

**GOALS AND OBJECTIVES OF SCIENCE FUNDAMENTALS OF
MECHANICAL ENGINEERING**

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Abstract: *The content and purpose of the science of the basics of mechanical engineering, indicators of the use of engineering structures, types of engineering activities and the relationship of science with other disciplines.*

Key words: *Technique, technique, technology, production, pedagogy, education.*

Engineering is the main activity of our latest advanced technology. Nowadays, more and more technologies are becoming technologies, and engineering activities are expanding. There are three stages in the development of technology. The first stage is the creation of technology based on iconic tools and technical experience, simply inefficient thinking (numbers, diagrams, calculations). Technical activity is understood as an additional power of man, spirit and god.

At the second stage, separate engineering measures are formed. They were divided into natural and artificial plans (Aristotle) and a new understanding of nature. F. Bacon writes that "in the new body" is a new kind of practice - engineering, human influence can do nothing, the division and unification of the body of nature, the rest of nature does in itself.

P.K. Engelmeyer, a common technical philosopher in Russia, believes that engineering is an art that interacts with nature, and that art produces results when it is understood. They believe that the knowledge gained from science should be recognized in accordance with the laws of nature. Philosophers understand nature differently. To this cardinal question, scientists of the New Age came to the idea of substantiating the knowledge gained from science in practice. The first of these was Galileo, an experienced observer who turned nature into an experiment. Which, the compatibility of theory and properties is technically determined in nature. Galileo proved that his theory was consistent with experimental measurements.

Since then, engineers have learned to determine the size of the natural impact necessary for technical purposes, build machines and mechanisms, and perform technical tasks necessary for humans. In addition to the works of Galileo, engineers Huggens, Hooke and others not only determined the choice of two types of objects (ideological and technical), but also created technical objects of a certain idea. The engineering design is an important engineering concept. This is a reality based on technology. At the beginning of

the 18th and 20th centuries, the main types of engineering activities were formed: engineering invention, design, engineering design.

An invention is a complete or partial form of engineering activity:

Inventive engineering determines the connection of all the main components of reality - the functions of an engineering structure, natural processes, natural conditions, structures (all components are located, recorded, calculated).

Design is an unfinished engineering activity.

The task of the design task is to determine the structural structure of an engineering structure, calculations determined in creative activity on the basis of relationships.

Construction is the process of constructing an engineering object in such a way that it satisfies the various requirements and conditions of the object (purpose, classification of performance, etc.), on the other hand, to find such a design and combine them, it is necessary to naturally provide the process and apply engineering building.

Engineering activity - the ability to improve the ability to use machines, machines, equipment and other tools involved in the production or service process; the use of alternative types of material resources, the search for new economical low-quality types; a set of skills, such as improving the management of an engineering facility.

Engineering ability is the extent to which a vehicle uses a mechanical mechanism. For example, 40 out of 100 automotive engineers work every day, 70 work under an engineer, and 30 of them are engineers.

Engineering ability is often measured by the utilization rates of engineering structures (cars, machines, buildings, equipment, tools).

Engineering service:

- constructive change;
- biological modification;
- removal of the control load;

The purpose of structural reforms is to improve the production of products by re-profiling and adapting machines and mechanisms to market requirements. This applies to engineering activities in the field of mechanical engineering. For example, every two years the product range of a modern enterprise is improved, otherwise the level of competitiveness of a machine-building enterprise in the international market will decrease.

The goal of biological transformation is to match the demand for agricultural products in the international and domestic markets. For example, efforts to increase the amount of fiber in cotton, the search for varieties that do not crush in the fruit, and other changes.

Reducing the managerial burden is often a reduction in the cost of a product or service by saving labor and material resources in the management process in the field of production and services. They are also looking for new elements of the competitiveness mechanism. Computerization and automation of many management processes in this area will reduce labor costs for management.

Increasing the search for elements of labor related to engineering activities. To do this, it is necessary to increase the level of skill by organizing the elements of labor

involved in each type of activity according to interests. For example, according to Japanese experience, each engineer must develop up to 12 proposals for different types of oils per year at the workplace, and up to 4 proposals for employees at the workplace. will develop competitiveness in the industry.

Biological modification improves the quality of agricultural products, in this area the state announces market demand for various types of products and, based on the results, organizes competitions.

Reducing the burden of governance - by creating strong laws in society, the interests of all people will be protected, and ultimately the cost of goods and services will be reduced.

The content of the basics of engineering, the subject of engineering: the current state of work, prospects for solving problems.

The purpose of the engineer's work is to ensure the efficient operation of the fleet, the economical use of labor and materials, the safety of moving vehicles for employees and the environment. The engineer is engaged in production technology, organizational management, design and research.

The purpose of the fundamentals of mechanical engineering is to develop objects of ground transportation systems, to train engineers to meet market needs.

The object of the study is the objects of land transport systems, car services, all types of car companies, car associations, car dealerships, transport departments of various ministries and organizations, technical means (rolling stock, equipment), equipment, computers and tools, measuring tools, etc.

Construction, design and calculations required special engineering knowledge (schemes, demonstrations, drawings), on the other hand, special knowledge. Initially, it had two forms - natural science (obtained or specially developed), personal-technological (design, technological operation, etc.). Later, the natural sciences were replaced by technical knowledge. The task in engineering design (when determining the design of an engineering structure) is solved by the project method: projects are simulated without the use of prototypes and a method of operation, construction, preparation of engineering equipment (machines, mechanisms, engineering structures) is assigned

It is recognized that the engineering and technical approach, the preparation of a structure based on calculations taking into account the impact of nature, allows it to differ from other preparations, where the impact of natural processes is either invisible (the direction of activity on other processes in general) or has shown that it is impossible to calculate, assign natural processes . Recently, engineering activity has become a product of culture and a privileged technique. Another factor that is adapting to the definition of technical reality is the growing importance of all confessions that contribute to the survival of society and humanity.

Depending on the process of production and service, an engineer is formed in accordance with it. In the production and operation of a car, the activity of an engineer is formed in different ways, and is also formed by the degree of use of raw materials, expressed in terms of the use of engineering structures in the operation of the car. For

example, the degree of use of an engineering structure was assessed by such indicators as specific fuel consumption, road utilization rate, load utilization rate, capacity utilization rate, load factor of machines, equipment, buildings and other facilities.

Requirements for a vehicle engineer.

The historical root of the word "engineer" is a Latin word meaning natural invention, knowledge and creativity.

The job of a talented engineer-inventor has the following characteristics:

1. Engineering work (position) includes the functions of management, control, preparation and organization of production;
2. Creation of new machines and equipment, tools and their introduction into production.
3. Engineering activity is connected with technological processes in production.
4. Collect scientific and engineering conclusions as a result of the collection and processing of information in the production process.
5. Facilitate manual labor, create a variety of equipment, use advanced technologies, introduce mechanization and automation.

He is a mechanical engineer with a higher education in the field of technical operation of vehicles, works in the automotive industry, car service system and manages the technical condition of vehicles.

The engineer's workplace is a parking lot, which means that he works with cars, trailers and other equipment.

An engineer must be able to make independent decisions, apply the results of scientific inventions in production, plan and organize the maintenance and repair of vehicles. Must be able to manage the reconstruction of transport enterprises, design work, the introduction of new technological processes, rationalization and invention, be able to maintain technical documentation of a transport enterprise, improve the skills of workers, calculate the economic efficiency of newly introduced equipment and methods. They need to test new equipment and technologies, work on computer technology, prevent injuries and occupational diseases at work, and protect the environment.

Must be able to find rational ways and means of maintenance and repair of vehicles.

An engineer who organizes the maintenance and repair of automobiles must be both a technologist, and a designer, and a designer, and an economist, that is, a universal specialist. Therefore, it is advisable to take these conditions into account when training personnel for vehicles.

The variety, variability and heterogeneity of working conditions at road transport enterprises require the engineer to make quick decisions. In general, a modern engineer, in addition to his professional and professional knowledge, must be a skilled psychologist, teacher, manager, able to find and influence the hearts of employees.

It was the engineering and technical approach that made it possible to prepare the design on the basis of calculations based on the effects of nature, recognizing that it differs from other preparations. It is impossible to calculate natural processes, to give tasks.

In the new era, culture and privileged technology became the product of engineering activity. Another factor that fits into the definition of technical reality is the growing importance of all acquaintances, society and human life.

The fundamentals of engineering are linked to a number of other disciplines. Before studying this subject, of course, a complex of disciplines related to the engineering field is included and taught in the system. For example, in the field of mechanical engineering, it is closely related to such technical sciences as mathematics, physics, chemistry, computer science, English, Russian, the theory of machines and mechanisms, strength of materials, the structure of machines and mechanisms. Science relies on the achievements of the sciences listed in its development path, works on scientific research, masters new aspects of the development of the region. If engineering activity is not based on the scientific achievements listed above, then the expected result will not be achieved and prices will rise.

Engineering works on road transport are as follows:

1. Measures in the process of maintenance (TSK) and current repair (T): development and implementation of modern methods of TKK for a faulty structure, reducing repair time, improving repair equipment and mechanisms, their application, increasing the level of technical safety.

2. Engineering activities in the automotive industry (TKK) and maintenance T: search for modern methods for determining the health of faulty nodes, bringing faulty nodes to the line, organizing start-up and adjustment work for drivers, using drivers in the established mode, driver or These include creating conditions for hunters and prevention of accidents and incidents.

3. Engineering and licensing activities include: development, supply and control of regulatory documents for vehicles; ensuring the collection of license fees; prevention of accidents and incidents; take measures to curb illegal activities.

4. To the operational activities of mechanical engineering: organizing the commissioning of wagons; control the operation of the error content; ensure the improvement of operational indicators (passenger, automobile * km, tons, tk * m, m * h); to prevent the occurrence of possible events and events in the content of the error.

5. Engineering work at the bus station: development of route documentation for faulty components; organize tenders to win them; organizing the departure of passengers and passengers; introduction of paid services (hotel services, catering and other services); organization of carriers for receiving and sending cargo; provision of separate rooms for privileged passengers; passenger insurance.

The science of the basics of mechanical engineering is constantly developing, based on the achievements of modern science in all areas. Therefore, it is by nature necessary that the foundations of science be continually renewed.

When training a specialist in an educational institution, he must be able to work independently upon arrival at the enterprise, acquire the necessary professional knowledge and skills, and be ready to minimize the period of adaptation;

In order to be able to succeed as a leader in the future, it is necessary to educate an employee who is able to draw the right conclusions and make the right decisions in different situations.

During the formation of engineers, the following requirements are imposed on him: to work as a technical engineer (engineer of the technical department, shop foreman, site foreman, ordinary designer, etc.). It is necessary to be ready to fulfill these tasks, to lay the foundation for its growth both horizontally and vertically. To do this, a specialist must have a deep understanding of the structure of the most common generations, the principle of operation, the theory and practice of its management;

Must be familiar with the rules of vehicle maintenance and the norms of working hours and material resources, components.

One of the most important requirements for an engineer is to make the right decisions and ensure their implementation in various standard and non-standard conditions of the transport industry.

Another requirement for an engineer is to ensure the constant growth of his knowledge (knowledge dynamism).

Expanding and updating knowledge requires constant work on oneself, getting to know new cars, studying the design of foreign-made cars, working with data, mastering new techniques and technologies.

During the period of study, the student must know the tasks, such as the implementation of a specific term paper and thesis, as well as the ability to work with other specialists.

During the training, employees will need to know each operation and experience in creating a normal psychological environment in the team.

In improving the quality of specialists, it is important to educate them in the spirit of responsibility, exactingness, high discipline and innovation.

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